

Ink of Integrity: The Role of Sudha Murty's Social Fiction in Shaping National Character

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Abstract:

*This research paper deals with *Wise and Otherwise*, a collection of 51 short stories, showcasing the myriad shades of human nature, from deep sense of duty and generosity to calculated meanness. The research argues that the "Character" of a nation is not an abstract concept but the collective sum of individual actions. Literature is a primary vehicle for fostering a sense of social responsibility and to inculcate moral values in society. Sudha Murty is famous for her status as a philanthropist and a writer of social fiction. Her writing portrays realistic picture of social issues and need for ethical values to make life meaningful. Her core philosophies are courage, humility, service, and cultural pride. She views social change as a moral duty arising from compassion and humanity. Murty's works deal with education, healthcare, women empowerment, rural development, ethical dilemmas and the spirit of India. This stories also explore the value of simplicity and integrity in a changing world. Murty depicts India's national character not as a single trait, but as a diverse fabric of contrasting behaviours. This highlights the importance of literature in building a shared national identity and cultural continuity.*

Keywords: Nation, character, integrity, social responsibility, values, cultural pride, individual, humanity

Introduction:

Sudha Murty is a celebrated Indian author, educator and philanthropist. Her works are the physical manifestation of her philosophy. The book *Wise and Otherwise* consists of 51 short stories based on the author's real-life encounters that left deep impact on reader's mind. Her simple stories preserve Indian folklore, traditions, and moral values, helping young readers understand their roots. She dedicates this book to those living in poverty but possess extraordinary minds and moral clarity. These stories are simple and conversational yet thought-provoking. She presents situations and lets the reader infer the wisdom or absurdity behind them. The tone is honest and deeply observational. Her writing is perfect blend of heart and brain so it enriches readers with emotions and wisdom. Her wise stories about incredible honesty, and otherwise

about human follies, highlighting, hypocrisy, greed, and the absurdity of people. Stories explore the divers, often contrasting, facets of life across India. Good stories create better people, and better people build a stronger nation. For Murty, nation-building is a cultural and ethical project facilitated by storytelling. ". *Wise and Otherwise* ultimately suggests that a nation is built not just by its infrastructure, but by the 'Moral fiber' of its people, which literature has a unique power to shape.

Honesty Comes from the Heart:

Hanumanthppa, a 15-years-old tribal boy, who receives scholarship of Rs. 300 every month for his education. He returns unused money because he did not attend the college for two months due to holidays and a strike. He showcases integrity, deeply rooted in the heart of

common person despite of extreme poverty. Honesty is an intrinsic value, not dependent on wealth or education. It springs naturally from the heart and is more valuable than money itself. Murty's characters teach the lesson through their actions rather than preaching. When individuals choose honesty like Hanumanthppa, they contribute to a national culture of trust and authenticity.

"Experience has taught me that honesty is not the mark of any particular class nor is it related to education or wealth. It cannot be taught at any university. In most people, it springs naturally from the heart." (p12)

In India, the Worst of Both Worlds:

A son abandons his elderly father in old-age home, telling the staff his father is a homeless stranger to avoid responsibility. He only returns after his father's death to claim the old man's inheritance. On the contrary father still kept his son as nominee in the bank, showing deep unconditional love. Murty highlights a growing moral decay in urban setting by saying to son, "It is shameful the way you and your father cooked up this drama for the sake of a few thousand rupees!" (p.28)

Cruelty and greed can corrupt family bonds. It serves as a stark reminder of our insensitive treatment of the elderly and the importance of filial duty. It's about losing traditional values of respecting elders, acting as a modern-day moral story to preserve cultural ethos.

In Sahyadri Hills, A Lesson in Humility:

Thandappa, an uneducated tribal chief, in the Sahyadri Hills, teaches the author about the grace and dignity of giving. Author visits Sahyadri Hills to distribute umbrellas and clothes. He refuses to accept charity without offering something in return. He eventually offers her a

bottle of wild honey and shows that one should not take without giving, regardless of how little they have. Thandappa insists on mutual respect and exchange. It directly teaches the value of a simple, grounded life and dignity even in giving and receiving – "There is a grace in accepting also". (p18)

On Human Foibles:

A teacher, boasted about his accomplishments to the author by claiming he won a gold medal. Author caught him in a lie because she had attended the same college and she was the one who won the gold medal that year. This made him cold and defensive. His lie is exposed, teaching a lesson in authenticity.

When The Mop Count Did Not Tally:

This story is direct reflection of the courage to do the right thing, even when it's difficult. A nurse courageously stops a surgery due to a missing mop because the mop count doesn't tally. Despite of doctor's anger and threat to dismiss her from job, she stands her ground. The missing mop was found on the floor, ultimately proving her right. Principals and following procedures are more important than hierarchy. One must have the courage to stand up to authority when it is a matter of right or wrong.

Forgetting Our Own History:

While receiving the Ojaswini Award for her work, Sudha Murty laments the ignorance of young Indians about historical women warriors. She feels our education system is lacking because it often omits the contributions of regional and female heroes. According to her importance of knowing one's own history instills pride, inspiration, and a sense of identity in the young generation. By showcasing historic examples of brave women like Rani Laxmibai, Kittur Chennamma, and Obavva who defied societal

norms and fought for justice, Murty emphasizes women empowerment for strong nation.

Powerful Politicians and Unsung Donors:

During a hospital inauguration, Sudha Murty observes how politicians bask in praise while genuine contributors are ignored. A humble villager's sincere offering contrasts with the political show. A charitable hospital built for the underprivileged. Politicians took the spotlight, while the real contributors and anonymous donors were ignored. She finds anonymous donors more sincere because they give without expectation of recognition or reward. True service lies in humanity, intention, and in silent service, not in public display.

What Is a Red-Letter Day? A Holiday:

On Independence Day, Sudha Murty is disheartened to find widespread apathy among students and teachers. The school was almost empty with teachers and students. They treated it as if as a day off. It is showing little enthusiasm of its significance. It highlighted a decline in national pride and respect for sacrifices made during the freedom struggle. Earlier, people celebrated with emotion, songs and patriotic spirit, not indifference. The story presents by Murty, to revive patriotism and teach younger generations the true meaning of independence, national pride and awareness. Patriotism must be instilled in younger generations through examples and education.

An Old Man's Ageless Wisdom:

Sudha Murty, chose an area, Kalahandi, known for poverty and underdevelopment. A tribal elder in Kalahandi surprises her with his views on ownership, money, and nature, showing real wisdom is found in simplicity. The old man believes people are disconnected from their roots due to money. He explains that nobody truly

owns natural resources, challenging modern, greedy perspectives on wealth and disconnection from nature. Tribals considered land, rivers, and air as gift from God, and did not believe in personal ownership. Despite having no modern education or wealth, an old and uneducated man possessed a deeper wisdom about life and nature compared to those connected with technology. Murty asks, "Who is more civilized—this wise old man in the Kalahandi Forest or those of us with our fingers on the pulse of the Internet?" (p25)

The story highlights the contrast between the simple, generous life of rural people and the complex, materialistic lives of urbanites. It is about understanding the profound, simple truth that nature belongs to everyone.

Conclusion:

Wise and Otherwise functions as a mirror held up to India. Through the lens of her individual encounters, Sudha Murty provides a layered view of the individual, the society they form, and the collective character of the nation. The work suggest that the individual is the fundamental unit of a nation's character. Each story is a case, highlighting personal choicesIt portrays society as a delicate web held together by trust, compassion, and unspoken duties. Many stories subtly reveal the deep societal divisions of class and caste. True societal health comes from mutual respect that transcends these barriers. The *Wise and Otherwise*, suggests that India's true strength lies not in its rapid economic growth, but in the timeless values of its people- honesty, gratitude, humility, and duty. A great nation is built on trust. The research pap argues that you cannot build a great nation without first building great individuals. The nation's character is not an abstract concept written in a constitution. It is the character of millions of individuals – the honest

poor student, the courageous young nurse, the generous tribal chief, and an old wise man.

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